

The Relationship Between Mental Workload and Usability in Website Interfaces: a Systematic Review

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Introduction

Web-based platforms play an important role in modern digital life, supporting services from healthcare to e-commerce (Wellman & Haythornthwaite, 2002). Users' mental workload while interacting with websites has been increasingly recognized as a key factor in shaping their preferences and satisfaction (Hertzum, 2025). While some studies have assessed website usability, there is still no quantitative review examining how cognitive load relates to usability ratings. The purpose of this study is to perform a meta-analysis to examine the relationship between mental workload and usability outcomes in the context of web-based digital interfaces.

Inclusion criteria:

- Studies conducted in the context of websites or web-based digital interfaces.
- Studies published from 2010 to 2025.
- Studies that include quantitative measurement of mental workload or cognitive load, such as:
 - NASA-TLX
 - Other structured cognitive/mental load assessments
 - Physiological proxies (e.g., EEG, heart rate variability, eye tracking)
- Studies that report usability-related outcomes, which may include:
 - System Usability Scale (SUS)
 - Task success rate
 - Time-on-task
 - Error rate
 - Satisfaction or ease-of-use scales
 - Learnability, memorability, or related constructs

Exclusion criteria:

- Articles not written in English.
- Studies that do not focus on websites
- Studies that lack either usability or mental workload/cognitive load measures.
- Qualitative-only studies or literature reviews that do not include empirical quantitative data.
- Articles without accessible full texts or incomplete statistical reporting.

Search Strategy:

The search will combine core concepts of web interfaces, mental workload, and usability. The following preliminary search string will be applied to databases such as Scopus, Web of Science, IEEE Xplore, and ACM Digital Library, with syntax adapted per database:

(TITLE-ABS-KEY (website* OR web*) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ("mental workload*" OR "cognitive load" OR NASA) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (usability OR SUS OR "system usability scale" OR "eye tracking" OR "Design optimization" OR SEQ OR "task completion" OR "error rate" OR "Time on task" OR Learnability OR Memorability)) AND PUBYEAR > 2009 AND PUBYEAR < 2026

Search results will be screened in two stages: title/abstract screening and full-text review based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria listed above.

References:

Hertzum, M. (2025). Understanding preference: A meta-analysis of user studies. *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies*, 195, 103408.

Wellman, B., & Haythornthwaite, C. (2002). *The Internet in everyday life*. Blackwell Publishers Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470774298>